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Anthraco­se disease- causing fungi, *Colletotrichum truncatum* (Schw.) changes the food value of tomato fruit.

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Abstract- *Solanum lycopersicum* L., often known as tomato, is a popular vegetable globally. Usually eaten in both raw and cooked forms, it possesses a high nutritional value. We have directly collected pathogens from diseased tomato parts obtained from both field and market sources in 10 distinct locations across Maharashtra. We achieve confirmation of pathogenesis by artificially inoculating an isolated, pure culture of the pathogen. *Colletotrichum truncatum* (Schw.) is responsible for causing anthracnose disease on tomato fruit. The infection primarily results in a significant decrease in lycopene content (57.142%), followed by vitamin C content (21.429%), total carbohydrate (20.512%), dietary fibres (18.645), reducing sugars (7.857%), and lipid content (6.25%). The nutritional composition of protein and free amino acids exhibits a small increase, with values of 0.2% and 6.173%, respectively.

Keywords – Anthracnose, Pathogen, Nutrient, Disease, Tomato

I. INTRODUCTION

Tomatoes, along with other plants such as potatoes, eggplants, and peppers, are classified as members of the potato family, which is often referred to as the nightshade family. This family has over three thousand species, the majority of which are economically significant. According to the literature that can be found on the tomatosphere website, there are over 7000 different varieties of tomatoes.

Due to the visual characteristics of tomatoes, Linnaeus placed them in the genus *Solanum* at the beginning of the year 1700. Philip Miller, another botanist, assigned it to the genus *Lycopersicon* about the middle of the year 1700. It is believed that the Aedan region of South America, which includes places like Peru, Chile, Bolivia, and Ecuador, is where the tomato originated. According to the history of tomatoes in America, there is evidence that the Aztecs and Incas were the first people to cultivate tomatoes. The tomato is classified as a vegetable, despite the fact that it is technically a fruit. Tomatoes are an excellent source of antioxidants, Vitamin C, potassium, folate, and vitamin K are all also found in high concentrations in these foods. A variety of colours, including orange, yellow, green, and purple, can be found in tomatoes, but when they are ripe, they are red.

A study that was conducted by Bhardwaj and colleagues in 2011 revealed that India is the second largest producer of vegetables, falling behind only China. It is estimated that 16.1 tonnes of vegetables are produced per hectare on average. When one considers vegetables, it becomes clear that they are an essential component of a well-balanced diet. Additionally, it is impossible to meet the daily requirement for main nutrients without the consumption of vegetables. The organisms that grow on plants and generate symptoms that make the plant weak and difficult to survive are referred to as plant pathogens, according to the definition provided by Hachiro Oku (1993). It is possible for a pathogen to develop on a variety of hosts; however, only a few cultivate on a particular host, while others grow on a

different host. Furthermore, the specificity of a pathogen might vary from one pathogen to another. Once more, fungi that are parasitic can be divided into two categories: obligatory and facultative parasites.

Pathogens attacking tomato plant can be categorised into following types by Dominique Blancard in (2012): air born bacteria, vascular and stem bacteria, air born fungi, root and stem base soil born fungi, soil born vascular fungi, viruses transmitted by seeds and contact, viruses transmitted by aphids, viruses transmitted by whitefly, viruses transmitted by thrips, viruses transmitted by nematodes, and nematodes attacking the roots.

Fungi are eukaryotic, achlorophyllous, unicellular or multicellular organisms that can reproduce by spores in an asexual or sexual manner. (Dongre, M. A., et al.,2023)

According to Berry (2007), tomatoes have a high-water content and a low-calorie count. This statement highlights the nutritional significance of tomatoes. Tomatoes are an excellent source of a number of essential nutrients, including vitamin A, vitamin B1, vitamin B2, biotin, folic acid, nicotinic acid, tocopherol, vitamin C, and vitamin K. In addition, in sufficient quantities, minerals can be found in fruit.

Of the total vegetables produced in India, 58% come from onions, 13% come from tomatoes, 7% come from brinjal, 5% come from cabbage, 4% come from okra, 4% come from potatoes, 4% come from cauliflower, 3% come from peas, and 5% come from other vegetables (Indian Horticulture Database, 2013, National Horticulture Board, Ministry of Agriculture, Government of India, India).

The comparative study of nutrients in diseased and control were done on Cabbage (Dongre M. A., Borse K.N., 2021), Coriander Dongre M. A., 2023), Spinach (Dongre M. A., 2022) and on leaves of Onion (M. A. Dongre, K. N. Borse, 2019).

II. MATERIAL AND METHOD

2.1 Collection site

In order to conduct a pathological investigation and a nutrient analysis on tomato fruit, samples were obtained from both the market and the field. In preparation for their eventual decomposition, they are maintained in a sterile state and stored at a cold temperature. Samples of the symptoms were obtained from several markets and fields in the state of Maharashtra. The pathogen was isolated and cultured in the laboratory in order to acquire a pure pathogen. Following the isolation and culture of the pathogen, we inoculated the newly isolated organism on healthy tomato fruit, thereby confirming its pathogenicity.

All ten locations are geotagged, and samples were collected from these ten sites in Maharashtra State. Specifically, the Konkan area, the Western region, the Marathwada region, the Khandesh or northern region, and the Vidarbha region are the five regions that make up Maharashtra, according to Omvir Singh et al. (2017). A minimum of two sites are being considered for the study, which amounts to ten different sites from all around the state of Maharashtra. (Table 1)

<i>Place of Collection</i>	<i>Geographical Data</i>
<i>Khandesh -Dhule</i>	<i>20°54'0" N, 74° 47'0" E</i>
<i>Khandesh -Jalgaon</i>	<i>21° 00'9" N, 75° 56'0" E</i>
<i>Konkan Alibag</i>	<i>18° 38'29" N, 72° 52'20" E</i>
<i>Konkan Sindhudurg savant wadi</i>	<i>15° 90'29" N, 73° 82'89" E</i>
<i>Vidharbha – Gondia</i>	<i>21° 45'88" N,80° 19'23" E</i>
<i>Vidharbha -Nagpur</i>	<i>21° 16'70" N,79° 08'52" E</i>

Marathwada Aurangabad	$19^{\circ} 90'18'' N, 75^{\circ} 36'22'' E$
Marathwada Latur	$18^{\circ} 40'02'' N, 76^{\circ} 58'83'' E$
West Maharashtra Pune	$18^{\circ} 50'46'' N, 73^{\circ} 83'41'' E$
West Maharashtra Kolhapur	$16^{\circ} 69'48'' N, 74^{\circ} 60'93'' E$

Table 1: Sites of diseased samples were collected.

2.2 Disease And pathogen

Anthracoze is one of the common diseases of Tomato plant during high humid condition. Seasonal records show that low temperature around $25 \pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$ with high humidity is favourable condition for growth. In Maharashtra such condition is seen during the months of June, July, August and September. 90% and above humidity is most suitable. The disease can also attack stem, leaves and other parts of plant.

- Causal organism: - *Colletotrichum truncatum* (Schw.)
- Genus - *Colletotrichum*
- Species - *truncatum* (Shwein.) Andrus & W.D.Moore (1935)

This disease is caused by the fungus *Colletotrichum truncatum* and occur primarily on fruit. Disease may be found on leaves along with other diseases.

Colletotrichum infect and damaging the fruit, the infection may be on green, immature fruit, but the symptoms occur on maturity of tomatoes, it may be pre or post-harvest condition.

The disease starts with small circular, dark spot. The spot will expand and forms concentric rings which are the fruiting bodies of fungus and contains spores.

During moist conditions, the fruiting body formation and release of spores are more intense, and in such conditions, rings look dark and creamy in colour. The infection is initially superficial, but as it progresses, pathogens invade the fruit and cause discoloration of the fruit. Ultimately, degradation starts and leads to a loss in quality and quantity of nutrients.

Colletotrichum truncatum (Shw.) Andrus and Moore were first reported by Andrus and Moore in 1935. It is a mitosporic fungus.

Figure 1: Diseased Tomato fruit (Anthracoze disease caused by *Colletotrichum truncatum*)

According to Cannon (2005), it has some synonyms, such as *Vermicularia truncate* and *Colletotrichum dematium* (Index fungorum, 2011).

There are 265 records of the occurrence of *C. truncatum* infection on several hosts. According to Farr and Rossmann (2011), families that are frequently attacked by this fungus are *Fabaceae*, *Poaceae*, *Solanaceae*, *Malvaceae*, etc.

Figure 2: Anthracnose site with acervulli and setae (*Colletotrichum truncatum* (Shw.))

Lycopene was estimated by Gordon Anthon and Diane M. Barrett in 2007.

III. OBSERVATIONS

The teleomorph of *Colletotrichum truncatum* has not been reported or may be absent. In anamorphic forms, the acervuli were circular. The conidia were hyaline, oval, or oblong in shape. Conidia present in the acervulum have long, septate, and pigmented setae with blackish hues and rounded basal cells.

The conidia are slightly curved, wider in the center, and gradually thinner towards the edge. At maturity, they become dark in colour and germinate from apical and basal ends. Colony appears on PDA medium, pale grey to dark grey, reverse dark brown. Mycelium is brown to dark brown; conidial length is between 19 and 30 μm ; width is 2.5 to 5 μm ; shape is falcate.

Pathogen morphology and microscopic observations are stated in Table 2, while Nutrient content in healthy and diseased plant were tabulated in Table 3 along with their comparison in percentage they changed after infection.

2.3 Nutrient analysis:

Total carbohydrate was estimated by the Hedge, J. E., and Hofreiter, B. T. (1962) Antrone method. absorbance at 630nm using a Systronics 2202 double-beam UV-visible spectrophotometer. Crude fibre is mainly composed of cellulose, lignin, and some minerals. After acid and alkali treatment, the cellulose and lignin were degraded. The initial and final weights after ignition at 600 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ give the crude fibre content in the sample. Reducing sugar was estimated using an arsenomolybdate reagent by following the method of Nelson-Somogyi. The Lawry method was followed for estimating protein. Oil was extracted through Soxhlet apparatus using petroleum ether as solvent, following the protocol given by Bligh, E.G., Dyer, W.J. (1959), and Sadasivam S. and Manickam (2005). The ninhydrin method was applied for the estimation of free amino acids.

Dry matter content and water content were analysed using the procedure given by Ruck (1969). Vitamin C content was estimated by using a 2,6-dichlorophenol-endophenol dye solution, a procedure given by Sadasivam and Manickem.

Figure 3: (Hyaline conidia and dark Setae) of *Colletotrichum truncatum*

Sr. no.	Place of Collection	Geographical Data	Culture appearance on PDA plate		Conidia length X diameter	Setae length X diameter
			Colour of colony	Appearance		
1	Khandesh -Dhule	20°54'00" N,74° 47'00" E	Greyish	Smooth	20.5 X 3.0 µm	136 X 5.4 µm
2	Khandesh -Jalgaon	21° 00'90" N, 75° 56'00" E	Grey	Smooth	28.2 X 4.8 µm	165.3X 6.0 µm
3	Konkan Alibag	18° 38'29" N, 72° 52'20" E	Dark Grey	Smooth	26.3 X 4.5 µm	143.2X 6.1 µm
4	Konkan sindhudurg savant wadi	15° 90'29" N, 73° 82'89" E	Grey	Smooth	19 X 2.5 µm	60.4 X 5.1 µm
5	Vidharbha- Gondia	21° 45'88" N,80° 19'23" E	Grey	Smooth	24.2 X µm	148.2X 5.6 µm
6	Vidharbha -Nagpur	21° 16'70" N,79° 08'52" E	Dark grey	Smooth	26.8 X 4.8 µm	161.8 X 5.8 µm
7	Marathwada Aurangabad	19° 90'18" N,75° 36'22" E	Greyish	Smooth	22.4 X 3.6 µm	125 X 5.3 µm
8	Marathwada Latur	18° 40'02" N,76° 58'83" E	Grey	Smooth	25.3 X 4.1 µm	154.3 X 6.1 µm
9	West Maharashtra Pune	18° 50'46" N,73° 83'41" E	Grey	Smooth	29.7 X 5 µm	172.4 X 6.1 µm
10	West Maharashtra Kolhapur	16° 69'48" N,74° 60'93" E	Dark grey	Smooth	27.1 X 4.6 µm	158.2 X 5.4 µm

Table 2: Collection sites and Pathogen characters (Morphology and Microscopic observations).

Sr. No.	Nutrient	Healthy	Diseased	% Alteration in nutrient
1	Water content	90 Grams /100 Grams	91.876 Grams /100 Grams	+2.084%
2	Total carbohydrate	3.9 Grams/ 100 Grams	3.1 Grams/100Grams	-20.512%
3	Reducing Sugar	2.8 Grams/ 100 Grams	2.2 Grams/100Grams	-7.857%
4	Fibres	1.18 Grams/ 100 Grams	0.96 Grams/100Grams	-18.645%
5	Protein	0.98 Grams/ 100Grams	0.982 Grams/100Grams	+0.204%
6	Lipid content	0.16 Grams/ 100 Grams	0.15 Grams/100Grams	-6.25%
7	Free amino acid content	0.81 Grams/100 Grams	0.86 Grams/100Grams	+6.173%
8	Vitamin C content	0.014 Grams/ 100 Grams	0.011 Grams/100Grams	-21.429%
9	Lycopene content	0.007 Grams/100Grams	0.003 Grams/100Grams	-57.142%
10	Dry Matter	10 Grams/100Grams	8.124 Grams/100Grams	-18.76%

Table 3: Nutrient analysis from healthy and diseased tomato fruit and % comparison of nutrient content.

IV. RESULT AND CONCLUSION:

Colletotrichum truncatum (Schw.) causes anthracnose disease on tomato fruit, in which major losses are seen in lycopene content (57.142%), followed by vitamin C content (21.429%), total carbohydrate (20.512%), dietary fibres (18.645%), reducing sugars (7.857%), and lipid content (6.25%). The nutrient values of protein and free amino acids are observed to be slightly elevated (0.2%) and (6.173 %), respectively.

Figure 4: Percentage alteration of nutrients after disease developed on ripe tomato fruit.

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